

Leaf Blade Structure of *Morus alba* L. and Resistance to Industrial Pollution

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Abstract

Trees can absorb toxicants and mitigate air pollution. *Morus alba* L. (Mulberry) is a well-recognized tree species that has high ecological plasticity and endurance toward adverse environmental conditions.

The structure of *Morus alba* L. leaf blades has been investigated in order to reveal its remarkable resistance performance toward industrially contaminated environment. Field observations showed that laminae of *Morus alba* L. were in good state and well-developed, without significant decrease of leaf blade surfaces, and with no chlorosis and necrosis, till the end of vegetation period.

Anatomical measurements registered greater leaf thickness of laminae from trees of polluted region. Under the industrial pollution the cuticle layer of adaxial surface increased, while from the abaxial side it decreased. In the adaxial surface epidermis have been detected idioblasts that perhaps strengthen the lamina surfaces and prevent from direct injury from air toxicants. The mesophyll structure of *Morus alba* L. expressed xeromorphic adaptation without noticeable air spaces in the spongy parenchyma naturally, and the spongy parenchyma seemed almost like palisade tissue, represented from palisade-like cells.

Key words: *Morus alba*, industrial pollution, leaf blade structure.

Introduction

The most popular tree in the world are believed to be *Morus alba* L. and *Morus indica* L. (de Almeida and Fonseca, 2000). Plants of *Morus alba* L. and *Morus indica* L. are generally grown for silkworm rearing and the genotype analyses support the opinion that *Morus indica* L. is merely a synonym of *Morus alba* L. (Gururajan 1960; Anonymous, 1962; Hirano, 1982; Vijayan *et al.*, 2006). Mulberry is a tree crop used in sericulture industry to feed the silkworm *Bombyx mori* L. and are cultivated throughout the world wherever silkworms are rearing (Duke, 1983; Jian *et al.*, 2012; Vijayan *et al.*, 2006).

Morus alba L. is a native to China, Cambodia, India, Indonesia, Japan, Laos, Myanmar, Pakistan, Thailand, Vietnam, Zanzibar, but it is a multipurpose tree widely planted in many tropical, subtropical and mild temperate regions of the world (Orwa *et al.* 2009; Gupta, 1993). White mulberry has wide ecological plasticity and becomes invasive in many places in the world viz., USA, Canada, South America, and South Africa. Mulberry is also grown on roadsides and avenues as an ornamental tree, invades old fields, urban lots, forest edges, and disturbed areas (Trees, 2010). It is one of the earliest woody plants under cultivation, broadly used in animal fodder, food production, as biomass fuel, for making high rank paper, in pharmaceutical industry, and in landscaping (Dai *et al.*, 2009; He *et al.*, 2005; Lin *et al.*, 2008; Qin *et al.*, 2010;

Srivastava *et al.*, 2003). Leaves are used as fodder for livestock, up to 6 kg per day, can improve cow's milk yield. Shade-dried leaves incorporated into feed enhance health and egg production in poultry (Orwa *et al.*, 2009). The mulberry's wood is suitable for many purposes: building house, boats, beams, posts, flooring, bridges, agricultural implements, cabinet work, furniture and turnery, especially picker arms, bobbins and tool handles; useful for spokes, poles, shafts and bent parts of carriages and carts; also much valued for sports equipment such as hockey sticks, tennis and badminton rackets, and cricket bats (Orwa *et al.*, 2009). As a fast-growing woody plant, *Morus alba* L. is characterized by deep roots, high resistance to pollution, wind, sand, drought, and salinity, with strong adaptability and easy cultivation, mulberry trees start to play roles in the prevention and control of desertification, water and soil conservation, saline-land management and returning the grain plots to forestry (Jian *et al.*, 2012). Mulberry trees are good carbon sink plants, leaves have high endurance and absorption to air pollutants such as chlorine, hydrogen fluoride, and sulfur dioxide (Lu and Jiang, 2003). The tree species has been used widely for ecologically viable water and soil conservation, maintaining soil fertility through litter fall and stabilizing physical soil structures (Orwa *et al.*, 2009; Jian *et al.*, 2012). The shade tolerant trees are highly susceptible to drought and inhabit ravines, valleys and coastal areas (Orwa *et al.*, 2009). For

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thousands of years mulberry cultivation has resulted in enrichment of mulberry genetic resources, and different biological characters, cultivation technology and mulberry industry development. It is predicted that in the future, mulberry ecological industries of different patterns will be established according to local land condition and market demand in different ecological areas (Jian *et al.*, 2012). In many studies *Morus* (*Morus alba* L.) has been recommended for green belt development in industrially polluted regions. Further, the species is a good performer having aesthetic value and ability to reduce air pollution (Orwa *et al.*, 2009; Jian *et al.*, 2012; Gupta *et al.*, 2016).

Attempt has been made in this paper to describe the structure of *Morus alba* L. leaf blades in order to reveal the registered high resistance performance toward industrially contaminated environment.

Materials and Methods

Characteristics of *Morus alba* L.

Morus alba L. is known as White mulberry, Russian mulberry, tut, mulberry, Silkworm mulberry, Moral blanco. Genus *Morus* are classified into 30 species, among which 15 are originally grown in China. In October of 2009, Botanical Journal of the Linnean Society modified the classification of *Morus alba* L to the order of *Rosales*, family of *Moraceae*, genus of *Morus* L. (Jian *et al.*, 2012).

Morus alba L. is a rapidly growing deciduous tree with a deep root system, either dioecious or monoecious, and sometimes can change from one sex to another. While high temperatures, strong light and long days favour maleness in mulberries, high humidity favours the production of female flowers. White mulberry is grown in cool temperate steppe to warm to tropical, very dry to moist, forest life zones and can be grown in annual temperatures ranging from 6-28°C, it is cultivated up to 3300 m in altitude (Duke, 1983). Mulberry trees can resist chilling and freezing of -30°C and endure high temperature of 40°C (Zhao, 2009).

Characteristics of the regions

The plant material was collected from two regions – one heavily polluted, situated around metallurgical factory “Kremikovtzi” (42°47' N; 23°30' E); and another, as a control from National Park Vitosha (42°30' N; 23°15' E). Kremikovtzi factory was emitting significant quantities of dust, SO₂, NxOx, CO, CO₂, H₂S, HCN, heavy metal etc. Various industries, vehicles and power generators are the major sources of SO₂ (Gupta *et al.*, 2015). SO₂ represents one of the main pollutants emitted by industrial combustion processes (Diab and Motha, 2007). Heat power stations and the “Kremikovtzi” metallurgic plant emitted 90% of the

total pollution amount in the region. The field from where the plant material was collected was at a distance of 2 km from the point source of main contamination.

Material and methods

The trees from the both fields were sun exposed with uniform height and growth form. Plant tissue samples were taken randomly, from the middle parts of the leaf blades and fixed in FAA - 90% ethanol (90 cm³); ice acetic acid (5 cm³); and formalin (5 cm³). Standard histological techniques were used to examine the anatomy of the leaf blades. All the sections were exposed to emission and examined under a light microscope. The measurements were repeated 30 times for each parameter, assessed statistically with t-test and photographed.

Results and discussion

Foliar injury is an earlier obvious response that is easy to quantify, and it is the most universally used measure of plant response to air contamination (Davis and Hilhour, 1976). In susceptible deciduous tree species the foliar injuries are over 50%; in moderately tolerant species they are normally less than 50% but more than 20%, and in tolerant ones are less than 20% (Nikolaevskiy *et al.*, 1971).

The visual observations of trees from Kremikovtzi region showed that one of the most tolerant deciduous tree species to this type of industrial contamination was *Morus alba* L. The leaf blades of *Morus alba* L. were in good state, well developed, without any sign of chlorosis and necrosis to the end of vegetation period, and without significant decrease of leaf blade surfaces that are usually mentioned in deciduous trees growing under air pollution (Sodnik *et al.*, 1987; Gupta and Ghose, 1988; Jahan and Iqbal, 1992; Kurteva and Stambolieva, 2007; Pourkhabbaz *et al.*, 2010; Assadi *et al.*, 2011; Appalasamy *et al.*, 2016). Leaf length is viewed as one of the qualities, which mirror the capacity of plant to ensure against stress. It is accepted that reducing leaf blade surfaces diminish the contact with air pollution and in this way plants improve their tolerance to the effects of implemented contamination (Assadi *et al.*, 2011). Mulberry has been classified as a first-class resistant tree species against sulfur dioxide pollution in its native region, so possibly the level of air contamination was lower of its tolerance threshold and thereby didn't cause that effect of reducing leaf blade surfaces. Mulberry also has high resistance to chlorine pollution and under such air conditions, mulberry leaves remained undamaged or part of damage was less than 20% of total leaf area, and hence leaves grew and developed normally (Lu *et al.*, 2004). In Poland, *Morus alba* L. also has been registered as tolerant species, growing near to copper smelter, leaf injuries were less

from <10% (Rachwa, 1983).

Plants adapted to changing environmental conditions by regulating the ratios of leaf anatomical structure (Tian *et al.*, 2016). Under the influence of air contamination have been registered faster linear growth at the beginning of vegetation period and strengthened the xeromorphic traits in the leaf structure of the tree plants from the contaminated region (Dineva, 2006).

The anatomical and morphological alterations that plants developed under different environment stresses and limitations depended from its genetic ability to tolerate those conditions, or from its ecological plasticity. The anatomical measurements of lamina cross sections recorded in this study are shown in table 1 and 2.

Table 1. Anatomical measurement of *Morus alba* L. leave blades.

Anatomical measurements (µm)	Mean (µm)		Standard deviation	
	treated	control	treated	control
Thickness of lamina (L)	120,81	114,43	±2,12	± 2,67
Thickness of upper cuticle (a)	4,60	4,09	± 0,57	± 1,018
Thickness of upper epidermis (b)	22,73	22,03	± 2,14	± 2,308
Thickness of mesophyll (m)	83,83	76,48	± 4,17	± 5,51
Thickness of the lower epidermis (e)	8,28	9,92	± 1,268	± 1,00
Thickness of the lower cuticle (f)	1,37	1,91	± 0,378	± 0,71

Table 2. Difference of means (µm), between polluted and control plants of *Morus alba* L.

Anatomical measurement (µm)	Difference of means (µm)
Thickness of lamina (L)	6,38*
Thickness of upper cuticle (a)	0,51*
Thickness of upper epidermis (b)	0,70
Thickness of mesophyll (m)	7,43**
Thickness of the lower epidermis (e)	-1,64***
Thickness of the lower cuticle (f)	-0,55**

p<0.05; ** p<0.01; *** p<0.001

Changes of leaf thickness

In the species of *Moraceae* leaf thickness displayed wide variability, in case of *M. serrata* Roxb. It has been reported that measured leaf thickness was about 240,35 ± 0,57 µm, while in case of *M. alba* L. it was 140,00 ± 1,98 µm, and in some genotypes 112 ± 2 µm (Vijayan *et al.*, 2006).

Less stomatal frequency and higher leaf thickness is correlated with greater adaptability to stress conditions in the wild mulberry species (Ravindran *et al.*, 1997), and very well associated with drought resistance (Susheelamma *et al.*, 1990). The increase of leaf thickness indicated high resistance of species to the kind of stress (Gostin, 2009). In the observed species greater leaf thickness from the trees of polluted region was registered (table 1), with significance at p<0.05 (table 2).

Changes of cuticle layers

In the examined species, the average thickness of the cuticle on the adaxial surfaces was thicker than the cuticle layer covered the abaxial epidermis (figure 1 to

6, table 1, 2). In the trees from the polluted region the adaxial epicuticular layer ranged from 4,60±0,57µm, while in the control trees the mean was 4,09±1,018µm. Under the industrial pollution the cuticle layer from the adaxial surface increased, while from the abaxial side decreased (table 1, 2). The thick cuticle is a xeromorphic sign and in plants subjected to gas impact is considered as a mechanism for protection (Ilkun, 1978; Ninova, 1970). *Morus alba* L. has been described previously as one of the most resistant species to fumes containing sulphur emitted from factory, and the author observed changes in leaf anatomy as establishment of thicker cuticle (Ninova, 1970).

Changes of epidermis

Cross sections of *M. alba* L. leaf blades were observed to show significant differences between the adaxial and abaxial epidermis (figure 1 to 6), such a difference is peculiar for the species and has been reported by Klimko (2016). On the adaxial surfaces were identified idioblasts (figure 1, 2, 3, 6), that is also very specific, and the *Morus* species can be distinguished by them from others, and even within

Figure 1. *Morus alba* L. – Kremikovtzi.
pm – palisade mesophyll; *sp* – spongy mesophyll;

mulberry cultivars (Klimko, 2016). The adaxial epidermis cells are larger with mean $22,03 \pm 2,308 \mu\text{m}$ for the control, and $22,73 \pm 2,14 \mu\text{m}$ for polluted trees, with no registered significant difference under the influence of contaminated environment (table 2). The abaxial epidermis was represented with small sized cells and covered with thinner cuticle layer, and under contamination they significantly reduce their parameters (table 1 and 2).

Changes of mesophyll

The lamina of *Morus alba* L. can be described as bifacial, bifacial leaf of dicots, which possess an upper epidermis above the palisade and a distinct lower epidermis, with heterogeneous isolateral leaf palisade parenchyma and the interior filled with spongy parenchyma (figure 1 and 5). The mesophyll was mainly represented from palissadic like parenchyma (figure 2, 5, 6). Strong development of palissadic parenchyma is a well-known change in the internal structure of leaves of Dicotyledoneae plants as a response to xeromorphic environments (Beinticinco *et al.*, 2011). Isolateral leaf anatomy is a property to be a xeromorphic feature and its development exclusively depends on solar radiation (Pyykko, 1966). Densification of the lacunar parenchyma occurs as a result of continued solar radiation and water deficit, the water deficit may contribute to reduce the intercellular spaces; which

explains well the absence of lacunar or spongy parenchyma (Vidal and Pognonec, 1984; Amara *et al.*, 2017). This parenchyma exists but is less differentiated and denser to the point where it does not appear (Amara *et al.*, 2017). It can also even mingle with the palissadic parenchyma due to the expansion of that tissue and the resemblances between them (Al-Saghir *et al.*, 2006). Change of mesophyll is a positive phenomenon for adaptation to drought: a reduction in intercellular spaces (densification of lacunar parenchyma) can participate in the limitation of water loss (Oppenheimer, 1961; Vidal and Pognonec, 1984; Amara *et al.*, 2017). Reducing the intercellular air spaces likely xeromorphic plants or plants growing in polluted sites cause limit the water loss and gaseous pollutants uptake, which is regarded as important trait that enable the tolerant and more resistant genotypes to avoid or to oppose the adverse effects of gas contamination (Giacomo *et al.*, 2010). Klimko (2016) observed the same that the spongy parenchyma in *Morus alba* L. was present in four layers of elongated, short cells without air spaces, and the inner and abaxial mesophyll layers were a palissadic-like spongy parenchyma (Klimko, 2016).

Calcium oxalate and carbonate crystals

In the samples from both places have been observed calcium oxalate as druses crystals (figure 1, 2, 3, 4) and

Figure 2. *Morus alba* L. – Kremikovtzi.

Cystolith-containing idioblast: CA – cap region; CP – cylindrical protuberance; Cr – crystal; V – vacuole

cystoliths (figures 1, 2, 6), located in the adaxial epidermis, such deposition of Ca have been described from Katsumata (1971); Sugimura *et al.* (1999); and Klimko (2016). The species from family *Moraceae* formed two types of crystals in the lamina, and according to them are classified as: species with existence of only calcium oxalate crystals; species with only calcium carbonate crystals; and species with calcium oxalate and carbonate crystals (Wu and Kuo-Huang, 1997). *Morus alba* L. deposited in the leaf blades calcium oxalate and carbonate crystals.

Calcium oxalate formation perhaps function for deposition of oxalate, which otherwise can be raised to toxic amounts, also might contribute to maintaining an ionic equilibrium (Sugimura *et al.*, 1999). The crystals are forming in the vacuole of specialized cells known as idioblasts (Marschner, 1995).

Ca crystal filled the vacuoles of idioblasts in mature leaves, while immature leaves had many idioblasts without Ca deposition (Sugimura *et al.*, 1999). Ca deposition can increase or decrease in response to changes of Ca^{2+} concentration in growth medium (Franceschi, 1989), and it is directly proportional to the increase in leaf age (Sugimura *et al.*, 1999). It was also

suggested that crystal idioblasts might play an important role in Ca metabolism and the pathogen-defense mechanism (Dixon *et al.*, 1991; Sugimura *et al.*, 1999).

In mulberry (*Morus* spp.), cystolith-containing idioblasts are developed in the adaxial epidermis of leaves (Katsumata, 1971). The best known calcium carbonate formations are the cystoliths, and according to their morphology, mulberry varieties can be classified. Besides the morphological studies, there is no information concerning the physiological significance of Ca carbonate formation, but it is thought that are physiologically active in the regulation of Ca, carbonic and bicarbonic ions (Klimko, 2016). From the cross-sections (figure 1, 2 and 4) can be mentioned that the Ca crystals are much more in the laminae of *Morus alba* L. from the polluted region than those of control (figure 5 and 6). The similar results were found from Tomašević *et al.* (2008), the leaves of *Aesculus hippocastanum* L. (Horse chestnut) and *Corylus colurna* L. (Turkish hazel) exposed to stressful air conditions were with numerous single or aggregated crystals.

Figure 3. *Morus alba* L. – Kremikovtzi.

Figure 4. *Morus alba* L. – Kremikovtzi.

Figure 5. *Morus alba* L. – Vitosha.

Figure 6. *Morus alba* L. – Vitosha.

Elemental analysis of idioblasts, made by Sugimura *et al.* (1999), showed that Si was localized in both, the cap region and the cylindrical protuberance, where as Ca was detected in a large crystal (figure 2). This site specific cellular localization of Si and Ca may be unique; it has not been found in idioblasts of other plant species (Sugimura *et al.*, 1999). The Si in mulberry idioblasts and silica deposited in epidermal cells is considered to have a defensive function against pathogen attacks by strengthening the cell wall in the cap region (Sugimura *et al.*, 1999), but that perhaps can also prevent adaxial surface of lamina and from direct injures of air toxicants. For *Morus alba* L. was reported very low interspecific genetic distance and DNA polymorphism 61,40% μm (Vijayan *et al.*, 2006), so there should not be a great difference in the observed characteristics.

Conclusions

Under the industrial pollution the cuticle layer from the adaxial surface increased, while from the abaxial side was decreased. Greater leaf thickness was registered for the trees of polluted region, where the epidermis of leaves was thick and cutinized. In the adaxial epidermis idioblasts have been detected, which are covered with silica according existed references, and that perhaps strengthening and prevent adaxial lamina surfaces from the direct injure of air toxicants. The mesophyll of *Morus alba* L. is specific with that, that there were no noticeable air spaces in the spongy parenchyma naturally, and the spongy parenchyma almost like palisade tissue, represented from palisade-like cells. In the leaf blades have been observed formations of Ca crystals like druses that are much more in laminae from polluted region. The observations suggest that leaf blades of *Morus alba* L. have unique structure, expressing xeromorphic anatomical characters, and giving to the species great ecological

plasticity under different stress environments.

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